

Research Article

Comparative studies on Seed Germination and Growth Performances of *Irvingia wombolu* (Millbr) Seedlings from Different Provenances

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ABSTRACT

Provenance variations among the seedlings of *Irvingia wombolu* from four sources in South-west of Nigeria were studied in the nursery. Matured fruit were collected from the four sources and quantitative character such as Fruit length, breadth, weight, and volume were measured from samples of the fruits. Germination and seedling growth were assessed. The seedlings were assessed fortnightly for total height, collar diameter leaf production and total biomass for twelve weeks. The data were subjected to analysis of variance. Fruits from Owena had the highest value of length (5.3cm); Diameters (3.4cm) and weight (19.3g). The fruit from Ishara source had the lowest values for all the fruit traits measured (4.2cm; 2.9cm; and 15.1gm) for fruit height, diameter, and weight respectively. Percentage germination as well as rate of germination varied among the sources with owena having 80%, Isara 18.7%, Uba 87.5%, and Jaja 84.4%]. Analysis of Variance revealed significant difference among the seedling from the four sources ($P < 0.05$). Seedling from owena had the highest height of 29.2cm and mean number of leaves of 10.5. The highest diameter 16.10cm was recorded among seedling from Uba. Relative Growth Rate (RGR), Net Assimilation Rate (NAR) and root/shoot ratios also varied among the sources. The results suggest mass selection of the species for effective genetic improvement.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of food to the well-being and existence of mankind cannot be overemphasized. The expression of mental ingenuity and intellectual versatility of an individual is a function of the quality and quantity of food intake. A nation cannot advance technologically and attain political stability without a secured food supply base for her populace. The forest supply various produce consumed by man (Okafor, 1991). These include a wide range of edible products obtained from wild fruit trees including nut and seeds used as staple foods or main dishes as well as those used as minor food supplement condiments, thickening agents and flavour, leafy vegetables, fresh fruits, fresh seeds, edible oil, spices fruits drinks as well as alcoholic and non alcoholic drinks (Leakey and Newton, 1994).

Okafor and Lamb (1994) noted that these edible forest products constitute important and cheap sources of vitamins, minerals, proteins, carbohydrates, fats, and their contribution to the diet of local people is often great. The dietary contribution of forest trees to improved nutritional status of mankind is further enhanced by the timing of their availability which often falls at strategic periods of general food shortage, particularly in Nigeria; of special importance is the timing of the availability of fruit of *Irvingia wombulu* which mature during the "lean

season" when conventional staple food such as cassava, yams, rice are yet to mature. (Okafor, 1991).

The ever increasing socio-economic development coupled with growing pressure for other land uses have contained measures to reduce the forest estate of Nigeria threatening the natural supply of these indigenous fruit trees. Thus, for sustainability of these indigenous fruit trees and prevention of their genetic erosion, there is an urgent need for their domestication and improvement for orchard establishment. Hamrick and Godt. (1995) reported the existence of variations within food yielding trees that could be exploited in their conservation, improvement and utilization.

Apart from the utilization of *I.wombulu* to the dietary needs of the people, there are huge economic returns from a single productive tree like citrus, mango and cocoa. Hence, this study carried out with a view to identifying and selecting superior genotypes among the provenance for the domestication improvement and multiplication of the species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two hundred fruits (200) were collected from a single tree in each of the four sources listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Sources of fruits and seeds for the investigations on provenance variation in *Irvingia wombulu*

S/N	Fruit/Seed Source	State	Country	Latitude	Longitude
1	Owena	Ondo	Nigeria	7° 15'	5° 10'
2.	Jaja	Edo	"	6° 49'	4° 52'
3.	Uba	Delta	"	6° 13'	7° 19'
4.	Ishara	Ondo	"	6° 55'	5° 45'

From each lot, 30 fruits were randomly selected for the measurement of weight (g); length (cm); diameter (cm) and fruit volume (cm³). Fruit weight was measured using the Metler balance while the length diameters were measured with a meter rule and vernier caliper respectively. Fruit volume was measure through the displacement method.

One hundred and sixty (160) fruits from each source were allowed to ferment for one week under room temperature and were gently depulped in water. Thereafter, the seeds were sown according to sources in germination boxes each measuring 90cm x 70cm x 7.5cm. The germination boxes were with top soil collected from the forest floor. Watering was done daily in the morning. Germinations were taken daily and germination was taken to have occurred when the plumule emerged above the surface. Germination was taken to have been completed when no further germination was recorded.

Thirty (30) uniform seedlings at the two-leaf stage from each of the four sources were transplanted

polythene-pots (16cm x 12cm x 14cm) filled with top soil collected from the forest floor. The transplant seedlings were kept under shade for one week before they moved out into the open nursery where they laid out in a completely randomized design. Seedlings from each source were labeled appropriately to enhance subsequent relocation and identification. The following parameters were measured fortnightly for twelve weeks viz: seedling collar diameter (cm); total seedling height (cm); number of leaves and seedling biomass. Seedling collar diameter and height were measured with the caliper and meter rule respectively. On each occasion, five seedlings were randomly selected from each source and carefully uprooted. Uprooted seedlings were then separated into root and shoot components. The total leaf area of each seed was determined using the grid method. Thereafter, root and shoot components of each seedling were oven dried for 24 hours at 80°C. The samples were allowed to cool before the dry weights were measured on Metler balance. The data obtained were used to compute the Relative Growth Rate (RGR)

and Net Assimilation Rate (NAR) following Oni (1989). The data were subjected to analysis of variance using SPSS Statistical Package, and the least Significant Difference (LSD) computed to identify significantly different means.

RESULTS

Fruit traits

Mean values of characters of fruits of *Irvingia wombulu* from four sources is shown in table 2. The coefficient of variability (%) was highest for fruit diameter (27.19%) and lowest (8.30%) for fruit length. Fruits from Owena had the highest values for length (5.31cm) and diameter (3.37cm); weight (9.30g) and volume (21.80 cm³). On the other hand, fruits from Ishara had the lowest values for fruit length (4.21cm); diameter (2.91cm) and 15.07g and 12.86cm³ for fruit, weight and volume respectively.

Table 2: Metrical characters of fruits of *Irvingia wombulu*.

Source (cm ³)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit Diameter (cm)	Fruit Weight	Fruit Volume (cm ³)
Owena	5.31	3.37	19.30	21.80
Jaja	4.74	3.01	16.40	18.50
Uba	4.94	2.94	17.02	19.13
Ishara	4.21	2.91	15.07	12.86
mean	4.80	3.06	16.94	18.07
CV (%)	8.30	27.19	18.01	16.75
Standard Error	±0.07	±0.15	±0.60	±0.58

CV = Coefficient of variability

Seed Germination

Commencement of germination (Days after Sowing-DAS) varied among the seed sources. Germination was first observed 16 DAS among the seed lots from Ishara; Jaja and Owena sources while the Seed lot from Uba commenced germination at 17 DAS. Percentage germination also varied among the seed sources. Seeds from Uba source had the highest percentage germination of 87.5 followed by Jaja with 84.4, Owena (80) and Ishara (78.7).

Growth

Height

Table 3 shows that there is significant difference at 5% probability level of probability in seedling height both in provenance and age. The interaction between provenances and age did not have any significant difference on seedling growth of the species (Table 3). Mean heights of the seedlings from the four provenances were significantly different from each other (Table4).

Diameter

Seedlings diameter growth differed significantly among the provenances and age of seedlings at 5% probability level (Table 3). However, the interaction between provenances and age did not show any significant difference on seedlings diameter from the four sources. Also, the mean diameter values of the seedlings from

the four sources were significantly different from each other (Table 4).

Leaf Production

Number of leaves differed among the seedlings from the four provenances. (The average number of leaves for seedlings from Owena was 10.5; Jaja (7.0); Uba (8.3) and Ishara (8.2). Both provenances and age showed significant effects on leaf production among the seedlings of *I. wombulu*. However, the interaction between provenance and age did not show any significant effect on leaf production among the seedlings (Table 3). The mean number of leaves of seedlings from Owena (10.5) and Jaja (7.0) were significantly different from each other. Also, the mean number of leaves of seedlings from Owena (10.5) and Ishara (8.2) were significantly different from each other. However, the mean number of leaves of seedlings from Uba (8.3) and Ishara (8.2) were not significantly different from each other.

Biomass production

Biomass productions among the seedlings were significantly different at 5% probability level in both provenance and age. The interaction between provenance and age did not show any significant difference on total biomass among the seedlings (Table 3). Least significant difference tests among the means of the four sources showed that there was significant difference among the seedlings.

Net Assimilation Rate (NAR)

A summary of the data on net assimilation rate is given in Table 5. In general, the data did not give any discernible trend for all the provenances. Negative values were obtained for seedlings from Ishara (-0.0001 - 0.23.gm/m²/wk) and Uba (-0.003 - 0.007gm/m²/wk) in weeks 4-8 while seedlings from Jaja had negative values all through except in weeks 4-6 (0.004gm/m²/wk). On the other hand, seedlings from Owena had positive values throughout the duration of the experiment.

Relative Growth Rate (RGR)

The relative growth rate data, which showed a very similar pattern to that of NAR Relative growth rate values, were negative for Jaja in weeks 2 – 4 (-0.10gm/m²/wk) and 10 – 12(-0.14gm/m²/wk), Uba (-0.25gm/m²/wk) and Ishara (-0.23gm/m²/wk) in weeks 6 – 8 (Table 5). On the whole, seedlings from Owena had the best performance followed by Ishara, while Jaja had the poorest performance.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Table for Mean height growth, stem diameter, leaf production and biomass production of *Irvingia wombulu*.

Parameters	Source of Variation (SV)	Degree of Freedom (DF)	Sum of Square (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	F.CAL	F.TAB.
Height	Provenances	3	430.02	143.34	37.72*	2.68
	Harvest Time	5	159.15	31.83	8.37*	2.29
	Provenances x Harvest Time	15	79.5	5.30	1.39	
	Error	93	353.4	3.80		
	Provenances	3	3.57	1.19	5.67*	2.68
Stem diameter	Harvest Time	5	29.15	5.83	27.76*	2.29
	Provenances x Harvest Time	15	3.15	0.21	0.00	
	Error	93	19.53	0.21		
	Provenances	3	178.05	59.35	17.05*	2.68
	Harvest Time	5	356.8	71.36	20.51*	2.29
Leaf production	Provenances x Harvest Time	15	62.55	4.17	1.20	
	Error	93	324.64	3.48		
	Provenances	3	66.0	22.0	5.20*	2.68
	Harvest Time	5	98.75	19.75	4.67*	2.29
	Provenances x Harvest Time	15	113.7	7.58	1.79	
Biomass production	Error	93	393.39	4.23		

* = Significant at 5% level of probability

Table 4: Follow up test (LSD) of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Mean height growth, stem diameter, leaf production and biomass production of *Irvingia wombulu*.

Provenances	Height (cm)	Stem diameter (cm)	Leaf production	Biomass production (gm)
Owena	30.2 ^a	8.0 ^a	13.5 ^a	8.8 ^a
Jaja	28.9 ^a	6.6 ^b	8.0 ^{ab}	5.8 ^b
Uba	21.9 ^b	7.1 ^b	10.3 ^b	7.5 ^{ab}
Ishara	27.1 ^a	8.0 ^a	10.2 ^b	8.3 ^a

* Means with the same letter are not significantly different (P > 0.05)

Table 5: Net Assimilation Rate (NAR) and Relative Growth Rate (RGR) in Seedlings of *Irvingia wombulu*

Provenances	PERIOD OF ASSESSMENT IN WEEKS									
	2-4		4-6		6-8		8-10		10-12	
	NAR	RGR	NAR	RGR	NAR	RGR	NAR	RGR	NAR	RGR
Owena	0.003	0.01	0.003	0.05	0.0002	0.005	0.0007	0.03	0.0003	0.001
Jaja	-0.004	-0.01	-0.10	0.15	-0.150	-0.60	-0.01	0.51	-0.004	-0.1
Uba	0.001	0.03	-0.003	-0.07	-0.007	-0.25	0.002	0.12	0.001	0.04
Ishara	0.003	0.09	-	-0.02	-0.23	-0.23	0.004	0.19	0.003	0.11
			0.0001							

*NAR and RGR measured in $\text{gm}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2}\text{wk}^{-1}$

Root/Shoot Ratio

Table 6 gives the summary of the mean values of root and shoot as well as the root/shoot ratio of the seedlings

from the four provenances. Seedlings from Ishara have a ratio of 1:2.4 followed by Owena (1:2.1) while seedlings from Uba had a ratio of 1:1.8.

Table 6: Root and Shoot biomass and Root/Shoot ratios in seedlings of *Irvingia wombulu*

Provenances	Root Dry weight (gm)	Shoot Dry weight (gm)	Root/Shoot ratio
Owena	76.3	156.5	1:2.1
Jaja	51.9	103.6	1:2
Uba	69.5	126.8	1:1.8
Ishara	64.8	155.2	1:2.4

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Irvingia wombulu is a fruit tree of commercial importance. Much of the value attached to the fruit in terms of price is related to its size. Thus, a tree that produces big-sized fruits in terms of length, diameter and volume coupled with good quality will enhance the financial earnings of the grower. The variations observed in fruit size of *I. wombulu* from the four sources considered in this investigation showed that this trait could be selected for in orchard establishment of the species. The rate and percentage germination of seeds are important factors in nursery and field establishment of forest crops. Seeds from Owena had the highest mean fruit weight and were the first to germinate among the four progenies. This agrees with the observation of Oni and Bada (1991) who reported significant positive relationships between seed size and seedling vigour in *Terminalia ivorensis*. Result of growth of seedlings from the four sources revealed some exploitable level of variations. For instance, the variations observed among the seedlings in height growth could be selected for in mixed plantings. Superior height growth coupled with appropriate leaf display may enhance the photosynthetic efficiency of the plant as well as its competitive ability. However, in orchard establishment where only intra-specific competition abounds, provenances with reduced height and crown growth may be favoured to avoid fruit harvesting problems on tall trees.

The relative growth rate refers to the increase in dry matter per unit area. Thus, when seedling is leafless or failed to produce additional leaves over a long period of time, the growth rate may be negative. Growth will

only occur when photosynthesis is in excess of respiration (Nwoboshi, 1992). The negative RGR obtained in some provenances, notably Jaja, is an indication of its poor growth rate which may not make such provenances suitable for selection in orchard establishment. Similarly, the differences observed in the values of the NAR within and between sources is an indication of differences in photosynthetic efficiency of the seedlings of the species.

Also, the negative values obtained in some of the sources could be due to reduction in the leaf resulting from disease infection during the investigation. These results suggest that, mass selection could be an effective tool in genetic improvement of *I. wombulu*. However, this should be accompanied by investigation on the reproductive biology to evolve an effective breeding programme for the species.

REFERENCES

- Hamrick, J.L, Godt, M.J.W. (1995): Allozyme diversity in plant species. In. Brown, A.H.D.; Clegg, M.T.; Kahler, A.L.; Weir, B.S. (Eds) Plant population Genetics Resources, 1-19, Sinauer, Massachusetts.
- Keay, R.W.J. (1989): Trees of Nigeria. Oxf. University Press 476pp
- LakeyLe, R.R.B. and Newton, A.C. (Eds) (1998): Domestication of tropical trees for timber and non-timber products. MAB Digest 17. UNESCO, Paris.
- Nwoboshi, L.C. (1992): Tropical Silviculture: Principles and techniques. Ibadan Univ. Press, Ibadan 333pp.

- Okafor, J.C. (1991): Improving edible species of forest products. In: UNASYLVA, FAO, Vol. 42 1991/2 165.
- Okafor, J.C. and Lamb, A. (1994): Fruit trees, diversity and conservation strategies. In: Leakey, R.R.B.; Newton A.C. (Eds), 1994. Tropical Trees: The potential for Domestication and the Rebuilding of Forest Resources. HMSO, London.
- Oni, O. (1989): The reproductive biology of a West African Hardwood (*Terminalia ivorensis* A Chev.) Ph.D. Thesis (Unpb). University of Ibadan 309p.
- Oni, O. and Bada, S.O. (1991): Effects of seed size on seedling vigour in Idigbo (*Terminalia ivorensis*) *Journ of Trop. For Scien.* 4(3) pp 215-224.
- Oni O. (1980): The reproductive biology of a West African Hardwood (*Terminalia ivorensis* A Chev.) Ph.D. Thesis (Unpb.) University of Ibadan. 309p.

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